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On a Hypersurface of a Generalized (α, β) - Metric Space

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Abstract

In 1985, Matsumoto. M., [6] has discussed the properties of special hypersurface of Rander's space with $b_i(x) = \partial_i b$ being the gradient of a scalar function $b(x)$. He had considered a hypersurface which is given by $b(x) = \text{constant}$. In this paper we have considered the hypersurface of a generalized (α, β) -metric space with metric given by (1.1) which is given by the same equation $b(x) = \text{constant}$. The condition under which this hypersurface be a hypersurface of the first, second and third kind have also been obtained.

Keywords: (α, β) - metric, hypersurface, angular metric, the reciprocal tensor, covariant differentiation, h- and v- covariant derivatives.

1. Introduction

The notion of (α, β) - metric was introduced in 1972 by Matsumoto. M., [5 & 6]. On the basis of Rander's metric which was attracted physicist's attention [3, 4]. A Finsler metric $L(x, y)$ in a differential manifold M^n is called (α, β) - metric, if the L is a (1) p -homogenous in the variables α and β ,

where $\alpha = \sqrt{a_{ij}(x) y^i y^j}$ and $\beta = b_i(x) y^i$ is one form of degree one.

We have a number of (α, β) - metric such as Rander's metric, Kropina metric, generalized Kropina metric, Matsumoto metric as examples. With respect to these metrics, several authors ([4], [5], [6],[7], [10], [11], [12]) where we obtained important result and theorems. In this paper, we take the (α, β) -metric given by,

$$L^n = C_1 \alpha^n + C_2 \alpha^{n-1} \beta + C_3 \alpha \beta^{n-1} + C_4 \beta^n \quad (1.1)$$

where C_1, C_2, C_3 and C_4 are constants and n is a positive integer.

If $C_1 = C_4 = 1$, $C_2 = C_3 = 0$ and $n = 1$, then we get Rander's metric

$$L = \alpha + \beta \quad [11]$$

In this way by giving different values to C_1, C_2, C_3, C_4 and n we get different type of (α, β) - metric discussed by several authors [8], [9] etc earlier. Therefore, the metric (1.1) has become too much interesting because it is the generalization of several (α, β) - metric. Therefore, we say this metric as generalized (α, β) - metric and space generalized (α, β) - metric.

In 1985, Matsumoto. M., [6] has discussed the properties of special hypersurface of Rander's space with $b_i(x) = \partial_i b$ being the gradient of a scalar function $b(x)$. He had considered a hypersurface which is given by $b(x) = \text{constant}$.

In this paper we have considered the hypersurface of a generalized (α, β) - metric space with metric given by (1.1) which is given by the same equation $b(x) = \text{constant}$.

The conditions under which this hypersurface be a hypersurface of the first, second and third kinds have also been obtained.

2. Preliminaries.

Let $F^n = (M^n, L)$ be an n-dimensional Finsler spaces with (α, β) given by (1.1) where

$\alpha = \sqrt{a_{ij}(x) y^i y^j}$ is a Riemannian metric in M^n and $\beta = b_i(x) y^i$ is a differential one form in M^n .

The derivatives of $L = (\alpha, \beta)$ with respect to and are given by

$$L_\alpha = L^{1-n} \left[C_1 \alpha^{n-1} + \frac{C_2 (n-1)}{n} \alpha^{n-2} \beta + \frac{C_3}{n} \beta^{n-1} \right] \quad (2.1)$$

$$L_\beta = L^{1-n} \left[\frac{C_2 \alpha^{n-1}}{n} + \frac{C_3 (n-1)}{n} \beta^{n-2} \alpha + C_4 \beta^{n-1} \right]$$

$$L_{\alpha\alpha} = L^{1-n} \left[C_1 (n-1) \alpha^{n-2} + \frac{C_2 (n-1)(n-2) \alpha^{n-3} \beta}{n} \right] + (1-n) L^{-1} L_\alpha^2 \quad (2.2)$$

$$L_{\beta\beta} = L^{1-n} \left[\frac{C_3 (n-1)(n-2) \alpha \beta^{n-3}}{n} + C_4 (n-1) \beta^{n-2} \right] + (1-n) L^{-1} L_\beta^2$$

$$L_{\alpha\beta} = L^{1-n} \left[\frac{C_2 (n-1) \alpha^{n-2}}{n} + \frac{C_3 (n-1) \beta^{n-2}}{n} \right] + (1-n) L^{-1} L_\alpha L_\beta$$

Where

$$L_\alpha = \frac{\partial L}{\partial \alpha}, \quad L_\beta = \frac{\partial L}{\partial \beta}, \quad L_{\alpha\alpha} = \frac{\partial L_\alpha}{\partial \alpha}$$

$$L_{\beta\beta} = \frac{\partial L_\beta}{\partial \beta} \quad \text{and} \quad L_{\alpha\beta} = \frac{\partial L_\alpha}{\partial \beta}$$

The normalized element of support $l_i = \dot{\partial}_i L$ is given by

$$l_i = L_\alpha y_i \alpha^{-1} + L_\beta b_i$$

$$l_i = L^{1-n} \left[C_1 \alpha^{n-1} + \frac{C_2 (n-1)}{n} \alpha^{n-2} \beta + \frac{C_3}{n} \beta^{n-1} \right] y_i \alpha^{-1} \\ + L^{1-n} \left[\frac{C_2 \alpha^{n-1}}{n} + \frac{C_3 (n-1)}{n} \beta^{n-2} \alpha + C_4 \beta^{n-1} \right] b_i \quad (2.3)$$

Where $y_i = a_{ij} y^j$, the angular metric tensor $h_{ij} = L \dot{\partial}_i \dot{\partial}_j L$ is given by

$$h_{ij} = P_0 a_{ij} + q_0 b_i b_j + q_{-1} (b_i y_j + b_j y_i) + P_{-2} y_i y_j \quad (2.4)$$

Where

$$P_0 = \frac{L L_\alpha}{\alpha} = \alpha^{-1} L^{2-n} \left[C_1 \alpha^{n-1} + \frac{C_2 (n-1)}{n} \alpha^{n-2} \beta + \frac{C_3}{n} \beta^{n-1} \right]$$

$$q_0 = L L_{\beta\beta} = L^{2-n} \left[\frac{C_3 (n-1)(n-2) \alpha \beta^{n-3}}{n} + C_4 (n-1) \beta^{n-2} \right] + (1-n) L_\beta^2 \quad (2.5)$$

$$q_{-1} = \frac{L L_{\alpha} \beta}{\alpha} = \alpha^{-1} \left[L^{2-n} \left\{ \frac{C_2 (n-1) \alpha^{n-2}}{n} + \frac{C_3 (n-1) \beta^{n-2}}{n} \right\} + (1-n) L_{\alpha} L_{\beta} \right]$$

$$P_{-2} = \frac{L}{\alpha^2} \left(L_{\alpha} \alpha - \frac{L_{\alpha}}{\alpha} \right) = \frac{L}{\alpha^2} \left[L^{1-n} \left\{ \left(C_1 (n-1) \alpha^{n-2} + \frac{C_2 (n-1) (n-2) \alpha^{n-3} \beta}{n} \right) \right\} + (1-n) L^{-1} L_{\alpha}^2 \right] - \frac{L^{1-n} \left(C_1 \alpha^{n-1} + \frac{C_2 (n-1)}{n} \alpha^{n-2} \beta + \frac{C_3}{n} \beta^{n-1} \right)}{\alpha}$$

The fundamental tensor $g_{ij} = \frac{1}{2} \dot{\partial}_i \dot{\partial}_j L^2$ is given by

$$g_{ij} = P_0 a_{ij} + P_0^* b_i b_j + P_{-1}^* (b_i y_j + b_j y_i) + q_{-2}^* y_i y_j \tag{2.6}$$

Where

$$P_0^* = q_0 + L_{\beta}^2 = L^{2-n} \left[\frac{C_3 (n-1) (n-2) \alpha \beta^{n-3}}{n} + C_4 (n-1) \beta^{n-2} \right] + (1-n) L_{\beta}^2 + L_{\beta}^2$$

$$P_{-1}^* = q_{-1} + \frac{L_{\alpha} L_{\beta}}{\alpha} = \alpha^{-1} \left[L^{2-n} \left\{ \frac{C_2 (n-1) \alpha^{n-2}}{n} + \frac{C_3 (n-1) \beta^{n-2}}{n} \right\} + (1-n) L_{\alpha} L_{\beta} \right] + \frac{L_{\alpha} L_{\beta}}{\alpha} \tag{2.7}$$

$$q_{-2}^* = P_{-2} + \left(\frac{L_{\alpha}}{\alpha} \right)^2 = \frac{L}{\alpha^2} \left[L^{1-n} \left\{ \left(C_1 (n-1) \alpha^{n-2} + \frac{C_2 (n-1) (n-2) \alpha^{n-3} \beta}{n} \right) \right\} + (1-n) L^{-1} L_{\alpha}^2 \right] - \frac{L^{1-n} \left(C_1 \alpha^{n-1} + \frac{C_2 (n-1)}{n} \alpha^{n-2} \beta + \frac{C_3}{n} \beta^{n-1} \right)}{\alpha} + \left(\frac{L_{\alpha}}{\alpha} \right)^2$$

Moreover, the reciprocal tensor g^{ij} of g_{ij} is given by [5]

$$g^{ij} = \frac{a^{ij}}{P_0} - S_0 b^i b^j - S_1 (b^i y^j + b^j y^i) - S_2 y^i y^j \tag{2.8}$$

Where

$$b^i = a^{ij} b_j$$

$$S_0 = \frac{P_0 P_0^* + \alpha^2 [P_0^* q_{-2}^* - (P_{-1}^*)^2]}{P_0 [P_0 (P_0 + P_0^* b^2 + 2 P_{-1}^* \beta + q_{-2}^* \alpha^2) + (\alpha^2 b^2 - \beta^2) (-P_{-1}^{*2} + P_0^* q_{-2}^*)]}$$

$$J = P_0 [P_0 (P_0 + P_0^* b^2 + 2 P_{-1}^* \beta + q_{-2}^* \alpha^2) + (\alpha^2 b^2 - \beta^2) (-P_{-1}^{*2} + P_0^* q_{-2}^*)]$$

$$S_0 = \frac{P_0 P_0^* + \alpha^2 [P_0^* q_{-2}^* - (P_{-1}^*)^2]}{J}$$

$$S_1 = \frac{P_{-1}^* P_0 + \beta [(P_{-1}^*)^2 - P_0^* q_{-2}^*]}{J} \tag{2.9}$$

$$S_2 = \frac{[P_0^* q_{-2}^* + b^2 \{P_0^* q_{-2}^* - (P_{-1}^*)^2\}]}{J}$$

The h v-torsion tensor $c_{ijk} = \frac{1}{2} \dot{\partial}_k g_{ij}$ is given by [5]

$$2 P_0 c_{ijk} = P_{-1}^* (h_{ij} m_k + h_{jk} m_i + h_{ki} m_j) + r_1 m_i m_j m_k \tag{2.10}$$

Where

$$r_1 = P_0 \frac{\partial P_0^*}{\partial \beta} - 3P_{-1}^* q_0, \quad m_i = b_i - \alpha^2 \beta y_i \quad (2.11)$$

It is noted that the covariant vector m_i is a non-vanishing one, and is orthogonal to the element of support y^i .

Let $\{j^i k\}$ be the components of Christoffel's symbol of the associated Riemannian space R^h and ∇_k be covariant differentiation with respect to x^k relative to this Christoffel's symbol, we shall use the following tensors.

$$2E_{ij} = b_{ij} + b_{ji}, \quad 2F_{ij} = b_{ij} - b_{ji} \quad (2.12)$$

Where $b_{ij} = \nabla_j b_i$

If we denote the Cartan's connection $C \Gamma$ as $(\Gamma_{jk}^{*i}, \Gamma_{0k}^{*i}, c_{jk}^i)$ then the difference tensor

$D_{jk}^{*i} = \Gamma_{jk}^{*i} - \{j^i k\}$ of $(\alpha, \beta) - metric$ space is given by [6]

$$D_{jk}^i = B^i E_{jk} + F_k^i B_j + F_j^i B_k + B_j^i b_{ok} + B_k^i b_{oj} - b_{om} g^{im} B_{jk} - c_{jm}^i A_k^m - c_{km}^i A_j^m \quad (2.13)$$

$$+ c_{jkm} A_s^m g^{is} + (c_{jm}^i c_{sk}^m + c_{km}^i c_{sj}^m - c_{jk}^m c_{ms}^i)$$

Where

$$B_k = P_0^* b_k + P_{-1}^* y_k, \quad B^i = g^{ij} B_j, \quad F_i^k = g^{kj} F_{ji}$$

$$B_{ij} = \left\{ \frac{P_{-1}^*}{P_0} (a_{ij} - \alpha^{-2} y_i y_j) + \frac{\partial P_0^*}{\partial \beta} m_i m_j \right\} / 2$$

$$B_i^k = g^{kj} B_{ji}, \quad (2.14)$$

$$A_k^m = B_k^m E_{00} + B^m E_{k0} + B_k F_0^m + B_0 F_k^m,$$

$$\lambda^m = B^m E_{00} + 2B_0 F_0^m, \quad B_0 = B_i y^i,$$

Here and in the following we denote 0 as contraction with y^i except for the quantities P_0^* , q_0 and c_0 .

3. Induced Cartan Connection.

Let F^{n-1} be a hypersurface of F^n , given by the equation $x^i = x^i(u^\alpha)$ suppose that the matrix of the projection factor $x_\alpha^i = \frac{\partial x^i}{\partial u^\alpha}$ is of a rank $(n - 1)$, the element of support y^i of F^n is to be taken tangential to F^{n-1} i.e.

$$y^i = x_\alpha^i(u) v^\alpha. \quad (3.1)$$

Thus v^α is the element of support of F^{n-1} at the point u^α . The metric tensor $g_{\alpha\beta}$ and the hv-torsion tensor $C_{\alpha\beta\gamma}$ of F^{n-1} is defined by

$$g_{\alpha\beta} = g_{ij} X_{\alpha}^i X_{\beta}^j, \quad C_{\alpha\beta\gamma} = C_{ijk} X_{\alpha}^i X_{\beta}^j X_{\gamma}^k \quad (3.2)$$

at each point u^{α} of F^{n-1} , a unit normal vector $N^i(u, v)$ is defined by

$$g_{ij} = \{x(u), y(u, v)\} X_{\alpha}^i N^j = 0, \quad g_{ij} \{x(u), y(u, v)\} N^i N^j = 1 \quad (3.3)$$

As for the angular metric tensor h_{ij} we have

$$h_{\alpha\beta} = h_{ij} X_{\alpha}^i X_{\beta}^j, \quad h_{ij} X_{\alpha}^i N^j = 0, \quad h_{ij} N^i N^j = 1 \quad (3.4)$$

If (X_{α}^i, N_i) denotes the inverse of (B_{α}^i, N^i) , then we have

$$X_{\alpha}^i = g^{\alpha\beta} g_{ij} B_{\beta}^j, \quad X_{\alpha}^i X_{\alpha}^j = \delta_{\alpha}^{\beta}, \quad X_{\alpha}^i N^i = 0, \quad (3.5)$$

$$X_{\alpha}^i n_i = 0, \quad N_i = g_{ij} N^j$$

$$X_{\alpha}^i \beta_j^{\alpha} + N^i N_j = \delta_j^i,$$

The induced connection $IC\Gamma = (\Gamma_{\beta\gamma}^{\alpha}, G_{\beta}^{\alpha}, C_{\beta\gamma}^{\alpha})$ of F^{n-1} induced from the Cartan's connection

$C\Gamma = (\Gamma_{jk}^{*i}, \Gamma_{0k}^{*i}, C_{jk}^i)$ is given by [6]

$$\Gamma_{\beta\gamma}^{*\alpha} = X_{\alpha}^i (X_{\beta\gamma}^i + \Gamma_{jk}^{*i} X_{\beta}^j X_{\gamma}^k) + M_{\beta}^{\alpha} H_{\gamma} \quad (3.6)$$

$$G_{\beta}^{\alpha} = X_{\alpha}^i (X_{0\beta}^i + \Gamma_{0j}^{*i} X_{\beta}^j) \quad (3.7)$$

$$C_{\beta\gamma}^{\alpha} = X_{\alpha}^i C_{jk}^i X_{\beta}^j X_{\gamma}^k \quad (3.8)$$

Where

$$M_{\beta\gamma} = N_i C_{jk}^i X_{\beta}^j X_{\gamma}^k, \quad M_{\beta}^{\alpha} = g^{\alpha\gamma} M_{\beta\gamma} \quad (3.9)$$

$$H_{\beta} = N_i (X_{0\beta}^i + \Gamma_{0j}^{*i} X_{\beta}^j) \quad (3.10)$$

and $X_{\beta\gamma}^i = \frac{\partial X_{\beta}^i}{\partial u^{\gamma}}, \quad X_{0\beta}^i = X_{\alpha\beta}^i v^{\alpha},$

the quantities $M_{\beta\gamma}$ and H_{β} are called second fundamental v-tensor and normal curvature vector respectively [6].

The second fundamental v-tensor $H_{\beta\gamma}$ is defined as [6]

$$H_{\beta\gamma} = N_i (X_{\beta\gamma}^i + \Gamma_{jk}^{*i} X_{\beta}^j X_{\gamma}^k) + M_{\beta} H_{\gamma} \quad (3.11)$$

Where

$$M_{\beta} = N_i C_{jk}^i X_{\beta}^j N^k \quad (3.12)$$

The relative h- and v-covariant derivatives of projection factor X_{α}^i with respect to $IC\Gamma$ are given by

$$X_{\alpha|\beta}^i = H_{\alpha\beta} N^i, \quad X_{\alpha/\beta}^i = M_{\alpha\beta} N^i \quad (3.13)$$

The equation (3.11) shows that h is generally not symmetric and

$$H_{\beta\gamma} - H_{\gamma\beta} = M_{\beta} H_{\gamma} - M_{\gamma} H_{\beta}. \quad (3.14)$$

Furthermore (3.10), (3.11) and (3.12) yield

$$H_{0\gamma} = H_\gamma, \quad H_{\gamma 0} = H_\gamma + M_\gamma H_0, \quad (3.15)$$

We quote the following Lemma which is due to Matsumoto [6]

Lemma (3.1): The normal curvature $h_0 = H_\beta v^\beta$ vanishes if and only if the normal curvature vector H_β vanishes.

The hyperplanes of first, second and third kinds are defined [6] we only quote the following.

Lemma (3.2): A hypersurface F^{n-1} is a hyperplane of the first kind if and only if $H_\alpha = 0$.

Lemma (3.3): A hypersurface F^{n-1} is a hyperplane of the third kind with respect to the connection $C \Gamma$ if and only if $H_\alpha = 0$ and $H_{\alpha\beta} = 0$.

Lemma (3.4): A hypersurface F^{n-1} is a hyperplane of the third kind with respect to the connection $C \Gamma$ if and only if $H_\alpha = 0$, $M_{\alpha\beta} = H_{\alpha\beta} = 0$.

4. The hypersurface $F^{n-1}(c)$

Let us consider a special (α, β) -metric (1.1) with a gradient $b_i(x) = \partial_i b$ for a scalar function $b(x)$ and consider a hypersurface $F^{n-1}(c)$ which is given by the equation $b(x) = c$ (constant).

From the parametric equation $x^i = x^i(u^\alpha)$ of $F^{n-1}(c)$, we get $\frac{\partial b(x(u))}{\partial u^\alpha} = 0 = b_i x_\alpha^i$, so that $b_i(x)$ are regarded as covariant components of a normal vector field of $F^{n-1}(c)$.

Therefore along the $F^{n-1}(c)$ we have

$$b_i x_\alpha^i = 0, \quad b_i y^i = 0 \quad (4.1)$$

In general the induced metric $\underline{L}(u, v)$ from the metric (1.1) is given by

$$\underline{L}(u, v) = c_1 \left\{ a_{ij}(x(u)) X_\alpha^i X_\beta^j v^\alpha v^\beta \right\}^{n/2}$$

therefore the induced metric of $F^{n-1}(c)$ becomes

$$\underline{L}(u, v) = \sqrt{c_1 a_{\alpha\beta}(u) v^\alpha v^\beta}, \quad a_{\alpha\beta} = a_{ij}(x(u)) X_\alpha^i X_\beta^j \quad (4.2)$$

Which is a Riemannian metric, at the point of $F^{n-1}(c)$ from (2.5), (2.7) and (2.9)

we have

$$\begin{aligned} P_0 &= C_1^{2/n}, & q_0 &= \frac{(1-n) C_1^{2(1-n)/n} C_2^2}{n^2}, & q_{-1} &= 0, \\ P_{-2} &= -C_1^{2/n} \alpha^{-2}, & P_0^* &= \frac{(2-n) C_1^{2(1-n)/n} C_2^2}{n^2}, & P_{-1}^* &= \frac{C_1^{(2-n)/n} C_2 \alpha^{-1}}{n} \\ q_{-2}^* &= 0, \\ J &= \frac{C_1^{(\frac{6}{n}-2)}}{n^2} [C_1^2 n^2 + (1-n) C_2^2 b^2] \end{aligned}$$

$$S_0 = \frac{(1-n) C_2^2}{C_1^{2/n} [C_1^2 n^2 + (1-n) C_2^2 b^2]} \quad (4.3)$$

$$S_1 = \frac{C_1 C_2 n}{\alpha C_1^{2/n} [C_1^2 n^2 + (1-n) C_2^2 b^2]}$$

$$S_2 = -\frac{b^2 C_2^2}{\alpha^2 C_1^{2/n} [C_1^2 n^2 + (1-n) C_2^2 b^2]}$$

Therefore from (2.8) we get

$$g^{ij} = \frac{a^{ij}}{C_1^{2/n}} - \frac{C_2^2 (1-n)}{C_1^{2/n} [C_1^2 n^2 + (1-n) C_2^2 b^2]} b^i b^j - \frac{C_1 C_2 n}{\alpha C_1^{2/n} [C_1^2 n^2 + (1-n) C_2^2 b^2]} (b^i y^j + b^j y^i) + \frac{b^2 C_2^2}{\alpha^2 C_1^{2/n} [C_1^2 n^2 + (1-n) C_2^2 b^2]} y^i y^j \quad (4.4)$$

Thus along F^{n-1} (4.1) and (4.4) lead to

$$g^{ij} b_i b_j = \frac{b^2 C_1^2 n^2}{C_1^{2/n} [C_1^2 n^2 + (1-n) C_2^2 b^2]} \quad \text{therefore we get}$$

$$b_i(x(u)) = \sqrt{\frac{b^2 C_1^2 n^2}{C_1^{2/n} [C_1^2 n^2 + (1-n) C_2^2 b^2]} N_i}, \quad b^2 = a^{ij} b_i b_j \quad (4.5)$$

Again from (4.4) and (4.5) we get

$$b^i = a^{ij} b_j = \sqrt{\frac{b^2 C_1^{2/n} [C_1^2 n^2 + (1-n) C_2^2 b^2]}{C_1^2 n^2}} N^i + \frac{C_2 b^2}{\alpha n C_1} y^i \quad (4.6)$$

Hence we have the following,

Theorem 4.2 : Let F^n be a Finsler space with (α, β) - metric (1.1) and $b_i(x) = \partial_i b(x)$. Let $F^{n-1}(c)$ be a hypersurface of F^n given by $b(x) = c$ (constant) suppose the Riemannian metric $a_{ij}(x) \delta x^i \delta x^j$ be positive definite and b_i be non-zero field then the induced metric on $F^{n-1}(c)$ is a Riemannian metric given by (4.2) and relation (4.5) and (4.6) hold.

Along $F^{n-1}(c)$, the angular metric tensor and metric tensor are given by

$$h_{ij} = C_1^{2/n} a_{ij} - \frac{2}{C_1^n} \alpha^{-2} y_i y_j + \frac{(1-n) C_1^{\frac{2(1-n)}{n}} C_2^2}{n^2} b_i b_j \quad (4.7)$$

$$g_{ij} = C_1^{2/n} a_{ij} + \frac{(2-n) C_1^{\frac{2(1-n)}{n}} C_2^2}{n^2} b_i b_j + \frac{C_1^{\frac{2-n}{n}} C_2 \alpha^{-1}}{n} (b_i y_j + b_j y_i) \quad (4.8)$$

From (4.1), (4.7) and (3.4) it follows that if $h_{\alpha\beta}^{(a)}$ denote the angular metric tensor of Riemannian metric $a_{ij}(x)$ then along $F^{n-1}(c)$, $h_{\alpha\beta} = C_1^{2/n} h_{\alpha\beta}^{(a)}$. From (2.7) we get $\frac{\partial P_0^*}{\partial \beta} = 0$ thus along $F^{n-1}(c)$, (2.11) and (4.3) give

$$r_1 = \frac{C_1^{(4-3n)/n} \alpha^{-1} C_2^3}{n^3} (n-2)(2n-1), \quad m_i = b_i$$

Therefore hv-torsion tensor becomes

$$C_{ijk} = \frac{c_2}{2n \alpha c_1} \left[(b_i h_{jk} + b_j h_{ki} + b_k h_{ij}) + \frac{c_1^{(2-3n)/n} c_2^2}{n^2} (n-1)(2n-1) b_i b_j b_k \right] \quad (4.9)$$

Therefore (3.4), (3.9), (3.12), (4.1), (4.5) and (4.9) gives

$$M_{\alpha\beta} = \frac{c_2}{2n \alpha c_1} \sqrt{\frac{b^2 c_1^2 n^2}{c_1^{\frac{2}{n}} [c_1^2 n^2 + (1-n) c_2^2 b^2]}} h_{\alpha\beta}, M_\alpha = 0 \quad (4.10)$$

Hence from (3.14) it follows that $H_{\alpha\beta}$ is symmetric.

Theorem 4.2: The second fundamental tensor v -tensor of $F^{n-1}(c)$, is given by (4.10) and the second fundamental h -tensor $H_{\alpha\beta}$ is symmetric.

Next from (4.1) we get $b_{i|\beta} X_\alpha^i + b_i X_{\alpha|\beta}^i = 0$ therefore from (3.13) and the fact that

$$b_{i|\beta} = b_{i|j} X_\beta^j + b_{i|j} N^j H_\beta \quad [6] \text{ we get}$$

$$b_{i|j} X_\alpha^i X_\beta^j + b_{i|j} X_\alpha^i N^j H_\beta + H_{\alpha\beta} b_i N^i = 0 \quad (4.11)$$

Since $b_{i|j} = -b_n C_{ij}^h$ from (3.12), (4.5) and (4.10) we get

$$b_{i|j} X_\alpha^i N^j = - \sqrt{\frac{b^2 c_1^2 n^2}{c_1^{\frac{2}{n}} [c_1^2 n^2 + (1-n) c_2^2 b^2]}} M_\alpha = 0$$

Thus (4.11) gives

$$\sqrt{\frac{b^2 c_1^2 n^2}{c_1^{\frac{2}{n}} [c_1^2 n^2 + (1-n) c_2^2 b^2]}} H_{\alpha\beta} + b_{i|j} X_\alpha^i X_\beta^j = 0 \quad (4.12)$$

It is noted that $b_{i|j}$ is symmetric. Furthermore contracting (4.12) with v^β and v^α respectively and using (3.1), (3.15) we get,

$$\begin{aligned} \sqrt{\frac{b^2 c_1^2 n^2}{c_1^{\frac{2}{n}} [c_1^2 n^2 + (1-n) c_2^2 b^2]}} H_\alpha + b_{i|j} X_\alpha^i y^j &= 0 \\ \sqrt{\frac{b^2 c_1^2 n^2}{c_1^{\frac{2}{n}} [c_1^2 n^2 + (1-n) c_2^2 b^2]}} H_0 + b_{i|j} y^i y^j &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (4.13)$$

In view of Lemmas (3.1) and (3.2), the hypersurface $F^{n-1}(c)$ is a hyperplane of the first kind if only if $H_0 = 0$.

Thus from (4.13) it follows that $F^{n-1}(c)$ is the hyperplane of first kind if and only if

$b_{i|j} y^i y^j = 0$. This $b_{i|j}$ being covariant derivative with respect to Cartan's connection $C \Gamma$ of F^n , it may depend on y^i . On the other hand $\nabla_j b_i = b_j$ is the covariant derivative with respect to the Riemannian connection $\{j^i_k\}$ constructed from $a_{ij}(x)$, therefore $b_{i|j}$ does not depend on y^i . We shall

consider the difference $b_{ij} - b_{ij}$ in the following. The difference tensor $D^i_{jk} = \Gamma^i_{jk} - \{j^i_k\}$ is given by (2.13), since b_i is a gradient vector, from (2.12) we have

$$E_{ij} = b_{ij}, \quad F_{ij} = 0, \quad F^i_j = 0$$

Thus (2.13) reduces to

$$D^i_{jk} = B^i b_{jk} + B^i_j b_{0k} + B^i_k b_{0j} - b_{0m} g^{im} B_{jk} - C^i_{jm} A^m_k - C^i_{km} A^m_j + C_{jkm} A^m_s g^{is} + \lambda^s [C^i_{jm} C^m_{sk} + C^i_{km} C^m_{sj} - C^m_{jk} C^i_{ms}] \quad (4.14)$$

But in view of (4.3) and (4.4) the expression (2.14) reduce to

$$B_i = \frac{c_1^{2(1-n)/n} c_2^2 (2-n)}{n^2} b_i + \left(\frac{c_1^{(2-n)/n} c_2 \alpha^{-1}}{n} \right) y_i,$$

$$B^i = \frac{(1-n) c_2^2}{[c_1^2 n^2 + (1-n) c_2^2 b^2]} b^i + \frac{c_1 c_2 n}{\alpha [c_1^2 n^2 + (1-n) c_2^2 b^2]} y^i$$

$$B_{ij} = \frac{c_2}{2\alpha n c_1} (a_{ij} - \alpha^{-2} y_i y_j)$$

$$B^i_j = \frac{c_2}{2\alpha n c_1} (\delta^i_j - \alpha^{-2} y^i y_j) - \frac{c_2^3 (1-n)}{2n\alpha c_1 [c_1^2 n^2 + (1-n) c_2^2 b^2]} b^i b_j - \frac{c_2^2}{2n\alpha^2 [c_1^2 n^2 + (1-n) c_2^2 b^2]} b_j y^i \quad (4.15)$$

$$A^m_k = B^m_k b_{00} + B^m b_{k0}, \quad \lambda^m = B^m b_{00}$$

By the virtue of (4.1), we have $B^i_0 = 0$, $B_{i0} = 0$ which give $A^m_0 = B^m b_{00}$, therefore we have

$$D^i_{j0} = B^i b_{j0} + B^i_j b_{00} - B^m C^i_{jm} b_{00} \quad (4.16)$$

$$D^i_{00} = B^i b_{00} = \left[\frac{(1-n) c_2^2}{[c_1^2 n^2 + (1-n) c_2^2 b^2]} b^i + \frac{c_1 c_2 n}{\alpha [c_1^2 n^2 + (1-n) c_2^2 b^2]} y^i \right] b_{00} \quad (4.17)$$

Thus paying attention to (4.1) along $F^{n-1}(c)$, we finally get

$$b_i D^i_{j0} = \frac{(1-n) c_2^2 b^2}{[c_1^2 n^2 + (1-n) c_2^2 b^2]} b_{j0} + \frac{c_1 c_2 n}{2\alpha [c_1^2 n^2 + (1-n) c_2^2 b^2]} b_j b_{00} - \frac{(1-n) c_2^2 b^m}{[c_1^2 n^2 + (1-n) c_2^2 b^2]} C^i_{jm} b_i b_{00} \quad (4.18)$$

$$b_i D^i_{00} = \frac{(1-n) c_2^2 b^2}{[c_1^2 n^2 + (1-n) c_2^2 b^2]} b_{00} \quad (4.19)$$

From (3.12), (4.5), (4.6) and (4.10) it follows that

$$b^m b_i C^i_{jm} X^j_\alpha = b^2 M_\alpha = 0$$

Therefore the relation

$b_{i/j} = b_{ij} - b_r D_{ij}^r$ and equation (4.1), (4.18), (4.19) give

$$b_{i/j} X_\alpha^i y^j = b_{i0} X_\alpha^i - b_r D_{i0}^r X_\alpha^i = \frac{C_1^2 n^2}{[C_1^2 n^2 + (1-n) C_2^2 b^2]} b_{i0} X_\alpha^i$$

$$b_{i/j} y^i y^j = b_{00} - b_r D_{00}^r = \frac{C_1^2 n^2}{[C_1^2 n^2 + (1-n) C_2^2 b^2]} b_{00}$$

Consequently (4.13) may be written as

$$\begin{aligned} \sqrt{b^2} H_\alpha + c_1 n \sqrt{\frac{C_1^{2/n}}{[C_1^2 n^2 + (1-n) C_2^2 b^2]}} b_{i0} X_\alpha^i &= 0 \\ \sqrt{b^2} H_0 + c_1 n \sqrt{\frac{C_1^{2/n}}{[C_1^2 n^2 + (1-n) C_2^2 b^2]}} b_{00} &= 0 \end{aligned} \tag{4.20}$$

Thus the condition $H_0 = 0$ is equivalent to $b_{00} = 0$, where b_{ij} does not depend on y^i . Since y^i is to satisfy (4.1) the condition is written as

$$\begin{aligned} b_{ij} y^i y^j &= (b_i y^i)(d_j y^j) \text{ for some } d_j(x) \text{ so that we have} \\ 2 b_{ij} &= b_i d_j + b_j d_i \end{aligned} \tag{4.21}$$

From (4.1) and (4.2) it follows that

$$b_{00} = 0, \quad b_{ij} X_\alpha^i X_\beta^j = 0, \quad b_{ij} X^i y^j = 0.$$

Hence (4.20) gives $H_\alpha = 0$. Again from (4.1), (4.21) and (4.15) we get

$$b_{i0} b^i = \frac{d_0 b^2}{2}, \quad \lambda^m = 0, \quad A_j^i X_\beta^j = 0, \quad \text{and } B_{ij} X_\alpha^i X_\beta^j = \frac{C_2}{2n\alpha C_1} h_{\alpha\beta}.$$

Thus (3.9), (4.4), (4.5), (4.6), (4.10) and (4.4) give

$$b_r D_{ij}^r X_\alpha^i X_\beta^j = - \frac{n^3 C_1^3 C_2 b^2 d_0}{4\alpha C_1^{2/n} \{C_1^2 n^2 + (1-n) C_2^2 b^2\}^2} h_{\alpha\beta}$$

Therefore the equation (4.12) reduces to

$$\sqrt{\frac{b^2 C_1^2 n^2}{C_1^{2/n} K}} H_{\alpha\beta} + \frac{n^3 C_1^3 C_2 b^2 d_0}{4\alpha C_1^{2/n} K^2} h_{\alpha\beta} = 0 \tag{4.22}$$

where

$$K = \{C_1^2 n^2 + (1-n) C_2^2 b^2\}$$

Hence the hypersurface $F^{n-1}(c)$ is umbilic.

Theorem 4.3 : The necessary and sufficient condition for $F^{n-1}(c)$ to be hyperplane of the first kind is (4.21) and in this case the second fundamental tensor of $F^{n-1}(c)$ is proportional to its angular metric tensor.

In view of Lemma (3.3) $F^{n-1}(c)$ is a hyperplane of second kind if and only if $H_\alpha = 0$ and $H_{\alpha\beta} = 0$ thus from (4.22) we $d_0 = d_i(x) y^i = 0$, therefore there exist a function $E(x)$ such that

$d_i(x) = E(x) b_i(x)$ thus (4.21) gives

$$b_{ij} = E b_i b_j . \quad (4.23)$$

Theorem 4.4 : The necessary and sufficient condition for $F^{n-1}(c)$ to be a hyperplane of the second kind is (4.23).

Finally (4.10) and Lemma (3.4) show that $F^{n-1}(c)$ does not become a hyperplane of the third kind.

Theorem 4.5 : The hypersurface $F^{n-1}(c)$ is not a hyperplane of the third kind

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